

Effect of Individualized Learning Strategy on Pupils' Academic Performance in Social Studies in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State

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ABSTRACT: Social Studies is one of the core subjects at the primary level of education which all pupils are exposed to. Despite the importance and relevance of social studies, the academic performance of pupils in the subject has been on a dwindling fall. The study investigated the effect of individualized learning strategy on pupil's academic performance in Social Studies in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State. The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, and control group quasi-experimental design. Four schools were selected using simple random sampling technique. The data collection instrument was the Social Studies Achievement Test (SSAT). The reliability coefficient of the instrument was obtained using PPMC at 0.74. Frequency counts, mean and percentage were used to analyse the demographical data of the participants. At the same time, all the null hypotheses were tested using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) all at 0.05 significance level. The results revealed that there was a significant main effect of individualized learning strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 24.714, P < 0.05$), there was no significant interaction effect of individualized learning strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = .936, P > 0.05$), there was no significant interaction effect of individualized learning strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 3.607, P > 0.05$), and there was no significant interaction effect of individualized learning strategy, gender, and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = .004, P > 0.05$). Based on these findings it was concluded that the effectiveness of individual learning strategy on pupils' academic performance, surpasses traditional instructional methods. However, the study findings suggested that the impact of individualized learning strategy on pupils' academic performance is not significantly influenced by gender, school type, in Ilorin west local government Kwara State. It was recommended among others that the effectiveness of individualized instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance, has been established. Consequently, teachers should be educated on the efficacy of using individualized instruction strategies in teaching pupils through well-organised seminars and workshops.

KEYWORDS: Social Studies, Individualized learning, Academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Social Studies, one of the fundamental and compulsory subjects offered at the primary level of education which is seen as an instrument for national development and building a strong Nigeria irrespective of ethnic and cultural differences. Adeyemi and Ajibade (2011) opined that the issues of desirable values, associations, and interactions can be addressed through Social Studies. Even though the inclusion of Social Studies in our school programme could be of great benefit, few gains have been made because of poor handling of the subject (Adekunle, 2011). The subject of Social Studies has been defined in various ways. The National Teachers Institute (NTI, 2000) stated that social studies is the process of education that emphasizes the connection of human beings with their physical and social worlds; Social Studies can cultivate a sense of national cohesion, loyalty, - and obligation to the nation. Mafuyae as cited in Clifford, Sunday and Joseph (2019) perceived that Social Studies touches the very core of our society. Social Studies in several nations of the world are essentially introduced to meet certain specific needs and aspirations of the people (Adeyemi & Onigiobi, 2020). In Britain for instance, Social Studies was introduced into the school curriculum after the first and second world wars as cure for social problems (Edinyang & Ubi 2013). Social Studies as a discipline is saddled with the responsibility of transmitting and instilling positive values into the citizens of this nation. In the opinion of Alberta as cited in (Adeyemi & Onigiobi, 2020), Social Studies has been accepted as a school subject that should help students to attain the basic knowledge, skills and positive attitudes needed to be responsible citizens and contributing members of society. Social Studies Education encompasses all aspects of societal development; be it political, economic, social, cultural, technological or educational. According to Adeyemi and Onigiobi (2020), in Nigerian context, the goals of Social Studies curriculum design is aimed at building

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a sound and balanced mind as a basis for functional social education directed towards the development of intelligent, responsible and self-reliant citizen.

A broad view of Social Studies was presented by Clifford, Sunday and Joseph (2019) when they described Social Studies as that aspect of school activity that includes the teaching of socially significant problems, questions, and topics believed to be relevant to the well-being of society. It is the development in the learner of the social and reflective thinking skills that would enable one to actively participate and effectively survive in the world through the rational collection, sorting, interpretation, analysis, and application of ideas (Clifford, Sunday & Joseph, 2019).

As valuable as the subject is to the moral and intellectual development of the child as well as the acquisition of required skills for building the nation, there have been gaps in the Nigeria Social Studies curriculum. Recently, in the educational sector, pupil's academic performance has been a matter of great concern to critical stakeholders; such as teachers who are the implementors of the curriculum, curriculum planners, the ministry of education, the federal government and the society at large. This poor achievement could be attributed to a number of factors such as lack of school facilities, lack of qualified social teachers, Social studies students' negative attitude to Social studies, Social studies language difficulties, Social studies teachers' interpersonal behaviors in Social studies classes, lack of Social studies students' motivation and interest, congested Social studies classroom, overloaded Social studies syllabus and poor instructional strategies used in teaching.

Social studies according to Oganwu as cited in Clifford, Sunday and Joseph (2019) efforts have been made to solve the problem of poor performance in the internal and external examinations in Social Studies by different stakeholders in the education industry, but evidence shows that the problems are still prevalent in our schools. Adeyemi and Ajibade (2011) asserted that the uninspiring performance of students in examinations reveals that an innovative teaching strategy that is interesting to teachers and helps students achieve their goals should be adopted in Nigerian primary schools. These strategies are numerous in which one of them is Individualized Learning Strategy.

Individualized learning strategy also referred to as individualized/personalized instructional strategy could be referred to those classroom practices of teaching which recognize the uniqueness of each student's learning. According to Olatoye, Aderogba and Aanu (2017), Individualized instruction is an instructional method in which the content, instructional materials, instructional media, and pace of learning are based on the abilities and interests of each individual learner. It is an instructional mode that is tailored to the need and ability of an individual learner (Mbakwem (2011).

Similarly, Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) stated that individualized instruction helps learners to learn at their own pace, be creative, enjoy learning activities, and be independent and more actively involved in their own learning. This strategy could assist the learner to proceed in a subject as far as his capability can permit. However, Cox (2016), states that individualized instruction consists of multisensory approach, scaffolding and tailoring instruction to suit students' interests. Other forms of individualized instruction could include personalized system of instruction, Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), audio tutorial and distance education.

Considering gender as a moderator variable, Bello and Famakinwa (2014) defined gender as the social and cultural construct, characteristics, behaviours and role which society ascribes to males and females. It is said to be one of the factors affecting students' socio-cultural and academic achievement. Our physical characteristics such as penis and vagina determine male or female respectively (Federal Ministry of Education, 2016). Some studies showed that gender influences academic performance. Amedu (2015) in a study on performance of male and female students taught Social studies with jigsaw instructional strategy stated that males performed higher than the females in biological associations. Aniodoh and Egbo (2013) reported significant differences between male and female students taught ecology with collaborative strategies in favour of females.

The influence of type in respect of schools and academic performance has always been given a separate attention to in which various findings are reported about the effects of school type on student achievement. Center of Education Policy (2007) and Abdulkadiroğlu et al. (2009) did not find statistically significant impact, but Angrist et al. (2011) found that studying at a private school has increased math scores by 0.2 standard deviations. Frenette and Chan (2015) also found 8% increase for private school students. On the other hand, Chingos and West (2015) ended up with a slightly negative effect of 0.041 standard deviations. Reçber, Işıksal, and Koç (2018) investigated if the achievement in mathematics of and the student attitude towards mathematics differ between public and private schools found that levels of achievement did not differ significantly but private school students' attitudes are more positive. Despite the concern of gender and school type with regards to academic performance of pupils in social studies, it has however been observed that different researchers have carried out studies on different learning strategies on academic performance while few have studied the effectiveness of individualized learning strategy on pupils' academic performance in social studies and also in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. Hence, this justifies the need to examine the effect of individualized learning strategy on pupil's academic performance in Social Studies in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Social Studies is one of the core subjects at the primary level of education which all pupils are exposed to. Despite the importance and relevance of social studies, the academic performance of pupils in the subject has been on a dwindling fall. Recently, Social

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Studies educationists and researchers have expressed worry concerning the poor academic performance of pupils in Social Studies, the nature of this problem has made stakeholders of Social Studies education to brainstorm on the causes of the problem and the way forward and it is was discovered that one of the causal effects lies with the teachers. It has been revealed that teachers use inappropriate teaching methods in the classroom. Several teaching methods have been investigated to foster solution to the poor academic performance among pupils but none has been seen to give a conclusive end to the poor performance in the subject. Some studies investigated the effect of collaborative learning while others focused on the effect of cooperative learning on pupil's academic performance in the study. It is as a result of this that this study therefore sought to find out the effects of individualized learning strategy on academic performance of pupils in social studies in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses was tested in this study at 0.05 level of significance

H₀1: There is no significant main effect of treatment on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State.

H₀2: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State.

H₀3: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State.

H₀4: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental design due to the suitability in establishing possible effect relationship. Factorial design of 2x2x2 was adopted to test the null hypotheses for this study. The first two factorial levels are experimental and control groups, the second factorial design level is gender occurring in either male (M) or female (F), while the last factorial level is school type which are private and public schools. The population for this study comprised all private and public primary school pupil's registered in schools in Ilorin West Local Government of Kwara State. A simple random sampling technique be used to select the schools for the experimental and control group respectively. Two schools were selected for the experimental group and two schools for control group.

The instruments that were used for this study are Social Studies Achievement Test specifically titled (SSAT) which was developed by the researcher as well as Social Studies Instructional Guide titled (SSIG). The returned test given to the participants were used in analysing the data for the study. Descriptive statistic (frequency count, and percentage) and inferential statistics (ANCOVA) was adopted. The decision was taken at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentage was used to know the total number of gender (male and female) and school type (private and public) and their percentage out of 100. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to assess group differences in dependent variable providing a clearer understanding of the effect of individualized learning and other variables on pupils' academic performance.

RESULTS

Testing Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

Table 1: Showing the summary of Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) on significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	13160.764 ^a	8	1645.095	4.677	.000
Intercept	23317.217	1	23317.217	66.296	.000
Pre-test	239.309	1	239.309	.680	.411
Individualised Instruction	8692.348	1	8692.348	24.714	.000
Individualised Instruction * Gender	329.323	1	329.323	.936	.335
Individualised Instruction * School type	1268.453	1	1268.453	3.607	.059
Individualised Instruction * Gender * School type	1.485	1	1.485	.004	.948
Error	53108.611	151	351.713		
Total	61500.000	160			
Corrected Total	66269.375	159			

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Table 1 data shows the significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. There was significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 24.714, P < 0.05$). The hypothesis is therefore rejected in the light of the result since the significant value (.000) is less than 0.05. This implies that there was significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

Table 2: Summary of Bonferroni's Post Hoc pairwise Comparison of the scores within the two Groups

Treatment	Mean Score	Experimental	Control Group
Individualised instruction strategy	61.5		*
Conventional Method	38.5	*	

Table 2 reveals the significant main effect exposed by table 1 is because of the significant difference among: Individualised instruction strategy and Conventional Group. Individualised instruction strategy refers to experimental group and conventional method known as control group. This implies that those taught or exposed to Individualised instruction strategy performed significantly better than those taught with Conventional method.

H₀₂: There is no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

Table 2 shows the significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. There was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = .936, P > 0.05$). The hypothesis is therefore not rejected in the light of the result since the significant value (.335) is greater than 0.05. This implies that there was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.

Table 2 shows the significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. There was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 3.607, P > 0.05$). The hypothesis is therefore not rejected in the light of the result since the significant value (.059) is greater than 0.05. This implies that there was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State

H₀₄: There is no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy, gender, and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.

Table 2 shows the significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy, gender, and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State. There was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy, gender, and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = .004, P > 0.05$). The hypothesis is therefore not rejected in the light of the result since the significant value (.948) is greater than 0.05. This implies that there was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy, gender, and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

One of the results originated from this study revealed that, there was significant main effect of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 24.714, P < 0.05$). This implies that individual pupils usually learn according to their abilities using different learning styles. This was in a relationship with the submission of Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) who conducted a study on effects of individualized instructional method on secondary school students' achievement in social studies in Onueke education zone of Ebonyi state. It was revealed that the mean achievement scores of secondary school students taught social studies using individualized instructional method was higher than the mean achievement scores of those taught social studies using lecture method. The result was also in tandem with the findings of Nwakolo, Adejoh and Okwara (2019) who investigated comparative effects of individualized and cooperative video based instructional strategies on secondary school students' achievement in Biology in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue state, Nigeria. The findings from the study revealed that individualized and cooperative video-based instructional strategies were effective in improving students' achievement in Biology.

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More so, other findings from this study stated that, there was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and gender on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = .936, P > 0.05$). This means that individualised instruction strategy is not gender sensitive and this was supported by Yusuf and Adigun (2010) who investigated the influence of gender, school type and location on students' academic performance in secondary schools of Ekiti State. Found that gender have no significant impact on student's academic achievements. The finding was also in support of the submission of Owodunni and Ogundola (2013) who carried out research on gender differences in the achievement of Nigeria students exposed to concept in electronic works trade through reflective inquiry instructional technique.

There was no significant interaction effect of individualised instruction strategy and school type on pupils' academic performance in Ilorin West Local Government Area, Kwara State ($F_{(1; 151)} = 3.607, P > 0.05$). The finding was in a relationship with the findings of Musibau and Johnson (2010) also examined the influence of school type, sex and location on students' academic performance in Ekiti state secondary schools. It was also revealed that school type, sex and location had no significant influence on students' academic performance.

In contrary to the above result, Nawaz and Vandana (2023) on the differences in secondary students' social studies achievement based on their sex, locality, and type of school management. It was revealed that significant difference was recorded in students' scores based on their demography and school type. Also, Cecilia and Archibong (2015) who examined the difference in academic achievement of students in both private and public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

CONCLUSION

The discussion highlighted the effectiveness of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance, surpassing traditional instructional methods. However, the study findings suggested that the impact of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance is not significantly influenced by gender, school type, in Ilorin west local government Kwara State. This underscores that the academic performance is not constrained by gender, or school type, but rather depends on the teaching method, communication, and pupil's active participation in the learning process.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The effectiveness of individualised instruction strategy on pupils' academic performance, has been established. Consequently, teachers should be educated on the efficacy of using individualised instruction strategy in teaching pupils through well-organised seminars and workshops.
2. Pupils' academic performance should not be determined based on their gender because, the factor has been discovered not to be strong factors that hinder pupil's academic performance.
3. Recognising that the effectiveness of individualised instruction strategy in fostering pupils academic performance is independent of whether children attend public or private schools, governmental bodies, curriculum developers (such as Federal and State Ministries of Education), school proprietors, and the National Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) should encourage and sensitise the teachers to make use of the variants of all the methods prescribed in the policy in teaching children.

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